

Public Service Performance Accountability: Case Study at Surabaya Zoo, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: The importance of accountability in the performance of public services greatly affects the trust and competence of the organization, especially PDTS Surabaya Zoo. This study aims to describe, interpret, and analyse the accountability of public service performance and analyse the accountability model of public service performance at the Surabaya Zoo. This study uses a qualitative research method with a case study approach. There are 4 types of accountabilities used to answer the research formulation, namely bureaucratic, political, professional, and legal accountability.

KEYWORDS: Accountability, and Surabaya Zoo, Performance, Public Service.

INTRODUCTION

Accountability is a prerequisite for the creation of a democratic and trustworthy government. Accountability means that a government agency or company has established and has a clear vision, mission, goals, and targets for work programs that have been, are being, or will be implemented. Accountability will also be able to measure how they carry out and maintain (hold) their responsibility for achieving results. Without a good accountability system, it is difficult to measure the performance of an agency or organization whether it has done well or not because there are no indicators to assess performance, vision and mission, and the goals to be achieved by an organization. Because basically accountability, there is an obligation to present and report all activities, especially in the field of financial administration aspects to higher level commitment makers. Therefore, accountability media is needed that is easy to access and easy to understand. For this reason, the media for accountability is not only limited to accountability reports, but also includes aspects of the ease of obtaining information, either directly or indirectly. So that accountability can grow in an environment that prioritizes openness as the basis for accountability [2].

One of the tourist attractions that characterize the city of Surabaya is the Surabaya Zoo (KBS). Surabaya Zoo is one of the tourism objects engaged in animal conservation institutions that have existed since 1916 under the name *Soerabaiasche Plantenen Dierentuin* by the Dutch East Indies Government [3]. The Surabaya Zoo in its journey has many problems including internal conflicts, a lot of news about cases in terms of legal aspects, employment, finance, animal deaths, management, and the lack of existing infrastructure, including the performance of KBS in providing services to the public. In addition, there was a dispute between the Regional Animal Park Company (PDTS) of the Surabaya Zoo (KBS) which is currently still happening, it is feared that it will disrupt the accreditation process, improve management at KBS and serve animal tourism visitors. The negative assumptions formed on KBS will automatically tarnish the image, and it is predicted that the number of tourist visits will decrease from year-to-year. Accountability for the management and implementation of good service performance for the zoo is very necessary because by performing optimal service performance and good management, this zoo can develop and progress. The Surabaya City Government's response to the problem was followed up by issuing the Surabaya City Regional Regulation No. 19 of 2012 concerning the Surabaya Zoo Animal Park Regional Company so that the existence of the Surabaya Zoo needs to be maintained and preserved and managed professionally.

The accountability report at PDTS of the Surabaya Zoo is carried out with three reports, namely daily reports made by the staff to the section head to be forwarded to the Head of Department, monthly reports made by the department head to the Board of Directors, and quarterly and annual reports made by the Board of Directors to the Mayor through the Supervisory Board. The report is an effort made by the PDTS of the Surabaya Zoo in realizing public accountability and transparency of both information and finance to the Surabaya Zoo's internal itself, the Surabaya City Government, and to the public. In this study, Public Service Performance Accountability at the Surabaya Zoo is seen based on the process which includes; level of accuracy, professionalism of officers, completeness of facilities and infrastructure, clarity of rules (including clarity of policies or laws and regulations) and discipline. Accountability for the performance of public services must be in accordance with the standards or deeds/promises of public services

that have been determined and must be accounted for which is then analyzed based on the accountability model. Romzek and Dubnick suggest 4 dimensions of accountability, namely bureaucratic, political, professional, and legal accountability. Seeing that there are still problems from managerial implementation and there is still little research on the accountability of public service performance, especially in regionally owned companies, one of which is the Surabaya Zoo. In addition, researchers provide recommendations for performance accountability models that are in accordance with the current conditions of the Surabaya Zoo which can be a solution in solving internal problems of the Surabaya Zoo to realize good and optimal Performance Accountability.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research is qualitative research with a case study approach. This approach refers to describing field events in detail and depth. Research with a case study approach is intended to understand as a whole and comprehensively related to the background of the problem, the situation, and the position of an event that is currently taking place, as well as all interactions in the social environment that are as they are. The focus of this research is as follows: (1) Public Service Performance Accountability at the Surabaya Zoo is seen based on Romzek and Dubnick's theory of accountability related to accountability in five forms of accountability, namely: bureaucratic, professional, political, and legal accountability. (2) Public Service Performance Accountability Model at Surabaya Zoo. There are several sources who became informants in this study with several criteria, including: 1). Have an understanding and master the research focus, 2). Have data and information needed by researchers, 3). Having direct involvement in the public service process at the Surabaya Zoo, 4). Willing to provide complete and accurate information. With consideration of these criteria, the informants in this study were the Surabaya city government, politicians, leaders, and employees of the Surabaya Zoo. The data analysis method used in this research is a case study analysis technique regarding the accountability of public service performance at the Surabaya Zoo, which follows the case study research method design proposed by Robert K. Yin. Yin (2015) explains that the analysis of evidence (data) in case studies consists of testing, categorizing, tabulating, or recombining evidence to designate the initial proposition of a study. Yin explained that the process of analyzing case study data based on the design of the case study method was divided into 3 steps, namely 1). Define and design, 2). Prepare, collect, and analyze, 3). Analyze and conclude.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Bureaucratic Accountability

On administrative accountability, it is known that it has been running. There is a submission of performance reports / business activities every quarter and annual financial reports after being audited by an independent auditor as well as reports on changes in the financial budget if there is a change in the budget to the regional head in this case is the mayor of Surabaya through the supervisory body as mandated contained in Regional Regulation Number 17 of 2014 concerning amendments to Regional Regulation Number 19 of 2012 concerning Regional Companies for the Surabaya Zoo (PD TS Surabaya Zoo), which daily reports are carried out by staff to the Section Head to be forwarded to the Department Head, monthly reports are made by the Department Head to the Board of Directors, quarterly reports and annually by the Board of Directors to the Mayor through the Supervisory Board. Based on the research results, there are 7 departments at the Surabaya Zoo, namely the Corporate Secretary Department, Business Development Department, Internal Control Department, Health Department, Conservation Department, Finance and Accounting Department, and Public Relations Department Resources General Affairs. Based on the results of interviews with researchers by 2 (two) divisions at PD TS Surabaya Zoo, namely the conservation department and the marketing department, it was found that the conservation sector has 3 departments, namely curator, animal health, and animal welfare. this is in line with the statement in the interview with the head of the conservation department as follows:

“Tupoksi dari kurator lebih kepada pendataan hewan, seperti keluar masuk hewan KBS, pencatatan kelahiran dan kematian. Tupoksi dari kesehatan binatang KBS ialah untuk menyusun nutrisi apa saja yang dibutuhkan oleh binatang, menyusun formulasi kesehatan binatang. Sedangkan untuk kesejahteraan binatang lebih kepada keamanan dan kenyamanan binatang yang berada di KBS itu sendiri seperti contohnya, pembersihan kandang dan hewan, pemberian mainan kepada binatang KBS agar tidak stress.” (The curator's main job is to collect data on animals, such as entering and leaving KBS animals, recording births and deaths. The main function of KBS animal health is to arrange any nutrients needed by animals, to formulate animal health formulations. As for animal

welfare, it is more about the safety and comfort of the animals in KBS itself, for example, cleaning cages and animals, giving toys to KBS animals so they don't get stressed).

Bureaucratic accountability is a strict hierarchical relationship between central accountability and the command implementing unit, both in formal and informal relationships. Based on the results of the study, administrative accountability in PD TS KBS is manifested by the existence of SOPs and/or Provisions in services such as: Provisions for Visitor and Recreation Services, Provisions for the Management of Animal Friends, Provisions for Event Management, Provisions for Trading in the KBS Area, Provisions for Entrance Ticket Sales Services, Tickets Special Entry and Tickets Other Than Admission Tickets. Therefore, PD TS KBS has carried out administrative accountability well according to theory.

2. Professional Accountability

Based on the results of research in the field, it shows that the embodiment of professional and moral accountability at PD TS KBS is not to distinguish between staff levels and structural officials in terms of imposing sanctions on abuse of authority or in matters that have negative impacts/other losses for the company and motivates them to continue progress and develop together in increasing awareness of the welfare of animals and employees as well as the sustainability of the company. Regarding rights and obligations, internal sanctions, assessment and evaluation, employee religious development, mental/psychological development, valid data have not been found. In this section, punishment and reward have been carried out to employees who violate or achieve innovation as stated in the statement from the head of conservation as follows:

"Kami memberikan SP sesuai dengan SOP yang berlaku, tetapi sebelum pemberian SP kami lakukan penyelidikan dan investigasi terkait kesalahan yang ada." ("We gave a warning letter (SP) in accordance with the applicable SOP, but before giving the SP we carried out an investigation and investigation regarding the errors that occurred.")

Performance appraisal is carried out on employees whose work contract is about to expire, this assessment is carried out by their immediate supervisor, then the employee gets an explanation of the results of the assessment to then be approved by both parties. Professionalism is the quality, quality, and behavior that characterizes a profession or people who are experts in their fields, or professionals. The term professional applies to all officers from the top to the bottom. Professionalism can be interpreted as a person's abilities and skills in doing work according to their respective fields and levels. Professionalism concerns the compatibility between the abilities possessed by the bureaucracy and the needs of the task, the compatibility between abilities and task requirements is a condition for the formation of a professional apparatus. This means that the expertise and capabilities of the apparatus reflect the direction and goals to be achieved by an organization [6]. Professionalism according to Sedarmayanti is a pillar that will place the bureaucracy as an effective machine for the government and as a parameter of the apparatus' skills in working well. The measure of professionalism is competence, effectiveness, and efficiency as well as responsibility [7].

3. Political Accountability

The power of political authorities to regulate, set priorities, redistribute resources and to ensure compliance with public program order and ultimately the survival of the organizations responsible for them, is a matter of political accountability. Based on the results of the study, political accountability in PD TS KBS is realized by the existence of a Financial Report (audited) at the end of each period of the current year to the Mayor of Surabaya through the Supervisory Board of PDTS KBS. Therefore, PD TS KBS has carried out political accountability well. Based on field observations in the development and planning of HR that the old management work culture is still strongly attached, so that sometimes there are conflicts of interest with employees who still show high loyalty to the old management even though they have worked at PDTS KBS, to deal with this problem the Surabaya Zoo Animal Park does periodic socialization of work culture and emphasizes to employees to be sensitive to environmental changes for effective and efficient KBS services. In addition, the director's strong leadership style makes almost all activities based on superior's instructions regarding the level of education, competence, motivation, and commitment so that there are still differences in the balance of competence in terms of scientific principles and experience/field practice of human resources. For this reason, the importance of a leader's approach to subordinates with a sense of taste but still prioritizing a culture of respect for superiors and subordinates to create flexible employees in responding to environmental changes and opening space for innovation for employees while still knowing the position of the main tasks and functions of each. Increased supervision as an effort to control services that are administrative and technical in nature and inculcating moral values is also considered important because it relates to increasing employee integrity in public services (honest, friendly, polite, responsible) [8].

4. Legal Accountability

The legal accountability of PD TS KBS is shown by the following regulatory guidelines:

- a) As a Regional Owned Enterprise (BUMD) it refers to Regional Regulation Number 17 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Regional Regulation Number 19 of 2012 concerning Regional Companies for the Surabaya Zoo.
- b) As a Conservation Institution that is guided by its rights and obligations as a conservation institution through SK.340/Menlhk/Setjen/KSA.2/5/2019 concerning Permits for Conservation Institutions in the Form of Zoos to PD Taman Satwa Surabaya Zoo in Surabaya City, East Java Province.

By law, PD TS Surabaya Zoo Number 17 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Regional Regulation Number 19 of 2012 concerning Regional Companies for the Surabaya Zoo Animal Park in article 5, namely as the basis for the establishment of the company as follows:

“Regional companies are established with the aim of: a. become a company engaged in the conservation of wild plants and animals outside their habitat (ex situ) which functions to breed and/or save plants and/or animals while maintaining the purity of the species, by prioritizing protected animals in Indonesia, in order to ensure the preservation, existence and its utilization; b. provide education, research, scientific development and healthy recreation services for the public benefit; c. to provide the best service to the community while still paying attention to the principles of animal welfare and being able to contribute to regional original income excluding regional taxes and regional levies; and/or d. participate in advancing the regional economy.”

Regarding the division of central and regional affairs/authorities, it can be referred to the provisions in Law Number 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government in article 10 which states that regional authority is a residue of the central government's authority which includes foreign policy issues; defence; security; justice; national monetary and fiscal; and religion. This means that apart from the six powers, it is purely a regional authority, both at the provincial and district/city levels. Based on this, the legal position of KBS here is clear, namely as a Regional Company (BUMD), then it fulfills one of the institutional criteria, namely BUMD and is engaged in conservation, education. This can be seen in Article 5 of the Surabaya City Regional Regulation Number 19 of 2012, that one of the objectives of the establishment of this PDS KBS is to become a company engaged in the conservation of wild plants and animals outside their habitat (ex situ) which functions for breeding and/or rescue. plants and/or animals while maintaining the purity of species, by prioritizing protected animals in Indonesia, to ensure their sustainability, existence, and utilization. Based on the four types of accountabilities according to Sinclair (1995) that occur in terms of accountability at the Surabaya Zoo, namely that the KBS in terms of legality has been clearly stated in regional regulations and has also obtained permission to become a conservation institution that regulates the start of determination as a regional company, election director to evaluation of programs and budgets per year. Administratively, it is known that there is an operational procedure system but, in its implementation, it has not run optimally, plus the human resources still need to be added in accordance with the required competencies. In terms of moral and professional management, performance continues to increase sensitivity to rapidly adaptive environmental changes, thereby reducing the impression of a static organization. Legally, the legal position of KBS is clear, namely through Regional Regulation No. 19 of 2012 as a Regional Enterprise (BUMD), which is engaged in conservation, education. This can be seen in Article 5 of the Surabaya City Regulation Number 19 of 2012, that one of the objectives of the establishment of the PD TS KBS is to become a company engaged in the conservation of wild plants and animals outside their habitat (ex situ) which functions for breeding and/or or saving plants and/or animals while maintaining the purity of species, by prioritizing protected animals in Indonesia, in order to ensure their preservation, existence and utilization.

CONCLUSION

Public Service Performance Accountability at the Surabaya Zoo in accordance with the theory of Sinclair (1995) can be concluded that:

- a) In terms of bureaucratic accountability, the form of regulations and basic rules from planning to evaluation already exist, but in organizational management it is still not optimally carried out by either the section head or department or employees.
- b) In terms of professional accountability and morality, inculcating a sense of responsibility and inequality between the number and quality of human resources in accordance with the company's needs, performance appraisals that are often found are not

in accordance with the reality on the ground carried out by the section or department head, making it difficult to analyse the needs and train employees of the Surabaya Zoo.

- c) In terms of political accountability, employees still have limited space to innovate and promote employees because the old management work culture is still strongly attached to prioritizing seniority.
- d) In terms of legal accountability, there is already a strong legal basis.

In terms of the accountability model for public service performance at PD TS Surabaya Zoo (KBS) that administratively and the LAKIP system is in accordance with SAKIP, the most crucial thing is the work culture related to professionalism and employee morality, therefore it is necessary to improve the resource management system. human resources, work culture and cooperative relationships with external parties as supervisors in the implementation of effective and efficient accountability.

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